

Exploring the Relationship Between Environmental Management and Property Rights

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Abstract: Markets function as institutions where individuals or firms exchange not only commodities but also the rights to use these commodities within specified conditions. The balance of supply and demand determines production levels and market efficiency. However, property rights—granting individuals control over resources such as land and capital—can lead to market inefficiencies by allowing manipulation of market outcomes. These inefficiencies, often referred to as market failures, are further amplified in the context of environmental and natural resource management. Incomplete systems of rights, coupled with the unsustainable use of public goods and natural resources, create significant challenges for market efficiency and environmental sustainability.

This study investigates how property rights influence market efficiency, focusing on their role in the mismanagement of natural resources and public goods. Using a survey of 30 participants, primarily students and middle-aged individuals, the research examines perceptions of legal ownership, its impact on natural market forces, and considerations of environmental effects when using public goods. The findings highlight the critical need for effective governance of property rights to address inefficiencies in resource allocation and promote sustainable environmental management.

Keywords: Property right, natural resource management, public awareness and participation, market efficiency, market failure, sustainable development.

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Introduction

Market is an institution in which individuals or firms exchange not just common commodities, but the rights to use them in a particular number of times (gravelle, hugh: and Ray rees, 2004). Supply and demand for goods determine the output level of any production. The terms market clearance and market failure are determined by the quantity supplied and quantity demand of any market. When both the quantity supplied and quantity demand meet equilibrium point it gives the indications that the market is working efficiently. The factors of production that are land, capital plays a very important role in any production legally any individual can own these factors of production and that is referred as the property right. These rights give the chance to manipulate and influence the market as by controlling the factors of production. That leads to an inefficient market or a market failure.

Literature Review

Private property rights allocate people to certain assets or resources including the rights to exploit or charge themselves. Since markets are institutions that coordinate the transfer of control over commodities, the nature of control is where rights are vested in the commodity. These rights provide the chance to control and steer the market as by controlling the production factors. Hence while an agent guides the commoditized use of their products, their control is always less than ideal. The reason for it is that the system of rights which stipulates that control is ill-defined is deficient. Thus, the manner in which producers and consumers apply environmental resources is made possible by the property rights regulating those resources, according to Tom Tietenberg. Rights as a term is defined as a set of privilege defining the owner's rights, stakes and restrictions for the use of the resource.

Market failure exists where there is inefficiency in distribution of goods and services where the demand of goods and services equals the supply of goods and services is then referred to as efficient market. But the market failure is a situation of allocation failure of resources. Several types of reasons can be attributed to such situation.

If an agent in a market attains the market power and is able to prevent occurrence of other mutually beneficial gains from trade then it is a market failure. In general, all these kinds of situations can lead to inefficiency and hence market failures.

Theoretical study

Property rights

One condition for optimal resource allocation in a market economy is the existence of efficient property rights, defined as meeting three specific requirements (Tietenberg 2000):

An efficient property right structure has three main characteristics:

Exclusive:

All of the benefits and costs arising out of owning and using the resource should accrue to one party.

Owner. This helps to overcome various issues with multiple owners of certain assets they fight over who will be proprietor and then no one invests. In the application of sustainable management systems.

Transferable:

Every property right must be equally alienable from one owner to another through bargain and sale, or by inheritance in a voluntary manner. This is to overcome the difficulty that owner is not investing

In resource improvements due to the fact that there is uncertainty in realizing other valuable benefits in the future.

Enforceable:

The rights in relation to property should be free from being removed or threatened by another person. Where property right cannot be protected or where risk of expropriation is standard.

It also eliminates owner action or interior investment in improvement or preservation of resources.

Property rights in this case have to be well defined because they help instill efficiency on resources utilized on the economic undertaking.

Along line of thought, other types of capital, such as investments in sustainable management practices. This suggests that where a market fails or is likely to fail in its operation the delivery of public good outcomes will be undermined because normally one or more of the preconditions is lacking. These efficient property rights however mean only that better management is not always instantiated (Pearce, 1990).

According to Tietenberg the owner of resource with well defined property a lot of incentive to use any given stock efficiently since any decline in value is a loss to the owner.

Alternative Property Rights Systems:

There are four main types of property rights regimes in the region to consider: open access, Historical development of communal tenure, individual tenure, and state tenure.

Open access:

Common property ownership is most well illustrated by open access where such problems are likely to occur. They are usually common, for the resource (e.g., land, fish) and most often, rights are not alienable. The access is unrestricted and therefore finally makes the property rights unenforceable. Individual users does not breathe cost of ownership. As a result, there are no disincentives for individuals to be responsible. Users' behaviour is rationally to over-utilize the resource to the maximum before the others could utilize it. In such circumstance the resource can be exhausted and this so often result in stock failure. Examples in the eastern and southern neighbouring countries include Tunisia with 11 scheduled offices and. Africa region are thus the destruction of Offshore and In land forests, over grazing of common lands and the hunting/ Butchering of the Black Rhino. In most instances exploitation of open access common property resources is associated with institutional and implementation failure. It is often the case that the local legislation and policy that address the question of resource management is either in its infancy or in any case weak, and not only at its developmental stage but also in terms of enforcement. Victoria is a joint freshwater body that crosses borders of the three East African nations of Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania. This is the largest fresh water Lake in the entire Africa. The lake is quite suitable for fish production because the sources of feed and food are readily available. The species of fish remains as a major product has increasingly shifted from being a diverse mix to predominantly the three species. This change has been occasioned by fishing activities, pollution, and introduction which has transformed into a keel species. The estimated maximum sustainable harvest estimated as 31,000 ton per year. However, production years on production years after 1981 have recorded more than this sustainable harvest. The annual harvest t in 1991 was nearly 1 80,000 tons of fish. Fishing is still quite good, but for certain key species the average catch per unit of effort has been declining steadily since 1986. These are clear signs so overriding, attributed most to inefficiency of property right of the resource.

Communal property

A community or a number of users control resource under defector The idea of communal property right Due to its applicability by a community or a number of users, the concept of communal property right is significant in the following features.

Ownership. While the actual land or the resources on that land may well be state owned, local people make decisions over the use of the land. One common error made by many policy makers is to overemphasise the resulting deterioration when there is a communal property situation. This is not true: However, this paper gives an equal and opposite reaction by pointing out that there are many examples of successful and sustainable resource management under a communal property rights regime. For communal wildlife management in Zimbabwe, there is what is called the "Campfire" programmed. Where restraint on resources is managed efficiently, ownership has

characteristics of being well-defined, exchangeable and enforceable. The major idea of this point is that possibility of access by encroachers has to be regulated. In many cases, sustainable management of communal resources depends on cultural and traditional practices. The communal property system can still Fail however. If users hold resources under defector

Ownership. The actual land or the resources on that land may in fact be owned by the state, but local people control management and use. A mistake by many policy makers is to assume that a communal property situation will always lead to resource degradation. This is not true: there are many examples of successful and sustainable resource management under a communal property rights regime. The "Campfire" program for communal wildlife management in Zimbabwe is a good example. Where resource use is regulated successfully, property rights tend to be exclusive, transferable, and enforceable. The most important point is that access by "outsiders" must be controlled. Often, sound communal resource management is linked to strong cultural and traditional practices. The communal property system can still Fail however. If there is a move from subsistence to less economic mode of production, some persons within the community may manipulate the system to obtain their own increments. Also, high

The population pressure and resource utilisation may in one or other cross the carrying capacity or deplete the stocks of the common resources since these are under communal control. In both cases if the resource base is a limited grazing area, putting more cattle into the area or if the resource is a given forest, felling more trees may at some point exert excessive pressure on the resource and consequently lead to its degradation.

State property

However, in most countries in the region, the government appears to own most of the natural resources. These include the state forests, national parks, inland waters and even the agricultural and rangeland managed under community systems. Management of the legal resources and ownership of the resources are vested in the state. In the state use of the resource the state disposes use through leases for the timber rights, safari areas, farming; permits for hunting, fishing, fuel wood, mining; quotas for fishing, timber and wildlife; it also in the case of the communal land recognizes traditional management rights and decisions over a resource al location. Sustainable resource management, however, may not always happen on state lands as the situation may begin to approach the open access situation. There is free access to resources (failure control). Resources utilisation by government agencies may not be properly monitored (institutional failure). Corruption in government can lead to excess resource exploitation; and High population pressure in areas around the resource may result to unauthorized utilization of resources. natural resources. Examples include state forests, national parks, inland waters, and even agricultural and rangeland held under communal management. Legal resource ownership and authority for management rests with the state. The state may allocate resource use through the form of leases (for timber rights, safari areas, farming), permits (for hunting, fishing, fuel wood, mining), quotas (for fishing, timber and wildlife) and in the case of communal lands, acknowledge traditional management rights and decisions over resource al location. Sustainable resource management may not always occur on state lands however, and might begin to mirror an open access situation. Some reasons for this market failure include:

- Control of access is not enforced (institutional failure);
- Monitoring of resources use by government agencies may be weak (institutional failure);
- Corruption in government can lead to excess resource exploitation; and
- High population pressure in surrounding areas can lead to illegal resource use.

Private ownership

Where option for minimum of three of the above condition in efficient property rights systems is available exclusive, transferable, enforceable then there is high propensity to private entities to handle resource Endurance. That is why most individual s will Support conservation when there are efficient property rights. But there can also be circumstances within the framework of the private ownership regime through which you can reach the degradation of resources. First, owners of the resource may have future uncertainty over the extent of the control on the ownership . If land expropriation could be a future eventuality – uncertainty of transferable rights – most reasonable users would not enter the development of the physical resource. LARGE SCALE COMMERCIAL FARMERS IN ZIMBABWE: ERIAL CONFUSED AFTER IN 1998 THE GOVERNMENT SOUGHT TO RESETTLE SOME FIRMS. This has led to decline of capital investment for the sector as a result of perceived risks. Second, in areas where there are very large extensively privatized areas it proves difficult to monitor and is expensive. This, in a way, leads to an open access issue – or enforcement failure when outsiders are granted the green light. The cases highlighted include the reduction of natural capital where large private lands that contain timber or wildlife are concerned.

Farmers are an example. Third, owners may only respond to government policies only on the matters of land utilization, prices, export incentives. For example, when using fertilizers, the farm owners might use them in the wrong proportions.

Chemical inputs or waste water if these are subsidized by the state. Furthermore, farm producer price and its supporting government policy for release of export crops which can change cropping pattern towards cash crops like tobacco that require more nutrients and water. Finally, the land owners may possess very low lower order physical capital in the form of human capital particularly knowledge and skills on how to manage the natural resources and environment sustainabl

Market system

Where option for minimum of three of the above condition of efficient property rights systems is available; (exclusive, transferable, enforceable), then there is high propensity that resource Endurance will be managed by private entities. As a result, due to the self interest, and the rationality that comes with it, most individuals will Support conservation under efficient property rights. But in any case there may be situations in the framework of the private ownership regime through which you can get degradation of resources. First, owners of the resource may face future uncertainty with reference to the restraints on their ownership. If it were conceived as a possibility that land may one day be expropriated – the transferability of rights is uncertain – most economically rational users would not undertake to develop the physical stock of the resource. Large Scale Commercial Farmers in Zimbabwe find themselves trapped in limbo after the government in 1998 proposed to resettle some of the farms. This has led to a decline in capital investment for the sector. Second, where there are very large disaggregate private land holdings, monitoring can be technically difficult and expensive. This is what Leads to an open-access problem also known as enforcement failure when outsiders are given access. It leads to the degradation of natural capital stocks such as timber or wildlife on large private.

Farmers are an example. Third, owners may only respond to government policies concerning use status, price incentives and exports. For example, when applying fertilizers, the owners of the farm may over do it.

Chemical inputs, or waste water if such inputs are subsidised by the state. Besides, farm producer price and its supporting government policy, policy over export crops could influence cropping pattern over cash crops such as tobacco crops which are neatly nutritious and water intensive crops.

Finally, from the stock of physical capital, it is alarming to note that owners of the land may have little or inadequate human capital, especially, knowledge and skills needed for sustainable protection of natural resources and environment.

'A market is an institution, the function of which is to bring together buyers and sellers, not just of goods, but of the right to use goods in specified ways for specified periods of time.' of time. Markets are institution which organise exchange of control of commodities, the nature of the control is conditioned, on the property rights associated with the commodities.'

Therefore an agents control concerning uses of commodities can be incomplete because the system of rights that denote that control is, to that extent, insufficient. Often this is divided into two broad categories of rights-excludability and transferability. Excludability concerns who is allowed to use an agent's commodity and for how long-and the cost of regulating this access. Transferability captures the freedom to delegate the right of using an agent to another agent such as selling or renting a product and the cost of transferring such right. That is, if a given system of rights does not guarantee these at minimal cost, then the resulting can be inefficient.

Externalities as a source of market failure:

One primary phenomenon is the most important aspect of the efficient property rights structure, namely the exclusivity. This characteristic is violated in most of the cession broad class of violations happen when an agent, involved in decision making, bears none or partial consequences of his actions. An externality occurs whenever the well being of some agents whether a firm or a household depends not only on own choices but also on choices made by some other agent. To illustrate the theoretical discussions let us consider two fictitious firms from the riverside area; one firm is in the steel industry while the other is in the hotel business. Now they also again have resolved on utilization of the river in various ways concerning their specific requirements. The steel firm uses it to dump factory wastes and the hotel provides natural recreation. The reason being, both have different owners and the sharing of the river will not be perfect. Therefore, we should assume that an efficient use of the water is going to happen. This occurrence is known as externality. The additional volume of waste deposited in the river placed an externality on the hotel costs a cost in the steel firm that could not reasonably be expected to be taken into account properly in refusing the volume of waste to discharge. Externality lead to the improperly define property rights system for instance public goods. Therefore, there is a phenomenon known as market failure situation.

Research questions

Property rights and how it leads to market failure:

The survey was based on the following few questions. The sample size was 30. The sample included people who are already out at the professional world including some freshly graduates . A few of them had experiences from working in the development sectors, mostly choose to interview those from whom I can portray the general situation of Bangladesh.

1. Can a legal ownership create a problem in the market?
2. Do you think that property right can affect the natural force of a market?
3. When you use any natural resource, you think about the effect on others?

Scope of study

The main objective is to find the relationship between property rights and market failure and how it impacts on the environment.

- i) Property rights and private property rights, alternative property right system.

- ii) Market system-market clearance situation. Market failure situation.
- iii) Relationship between the market efficiency and property rights.
- iv) Environment and property rights and the relation that exists.

Methodology

It is based on primary /primary data collected by interview /and finding from it and the secondary research collected from various sources & referencing . I have used secondary data gathered from textbooks, journals, internet and other research papers as means for carrying out the following secondary research. Data gathered from approved online web sites.

Results and Discussion

The survey was based on a short questioner; the sample group was randomly picked. From various fields of jobs. the idea of property rights and private property rights has a great impact on market but the real realization has that not much practice among general consumers or users of these resources. The imperfect allocation of resources causes market failure but this concept or the relation between these two factors are not that much cleared among the general people of our country. Of the entire question the major ones are given below-

1. Can a legal ownership create a problem in the market?

Out of 30 people 7 said yes, 6 said no and 17 said that they are not sure.

In regards of another major research question-

‘When you use any public good or natural resource you think about the effect on others?’

The options for answering consisted of - yes, no and may be. This question was directly related with the moral judgment and awareness about using surrounding natural resource.

Findings-

The answers of these question show that a 20 out of 30 said that they are not bothered about it. That is almost 61% of general perplex who do are not concern about the fact of overexploitation or miss use.

The next questions that were about the negative relationship of inefficient property rights and environment

Do you think that the absence of clearly define property rights can cause inefficient allocation of resource thus effect the environment?

The survey shows that most people are unaware of the relationship between these two factors. As the effect cannot be seen directly or the reason that the effect on environment is not understood directly, so people cannot relate the possibility of an environmental damage with the practice of inefficient property rights.

#When you use any public good or natural resource you think about the effect on others?

#In your apartment lift's capacity is to take maximum 40kg but some residence regularly uses the lift to carry weights more than 40kg and for that frequently the lift is out of order, what is your opinion about it? ----

These were the last two questions in the questioner. Both of them were situational, with the intention of finding out what general people would do or usually do in that kind of day-to-day situation. The answers were not very much clear. The questions Cleary state two situations such as "do you think about the effect when you use any resource? Or do you think about the effect towards others of your part of use?" The major number of participants shared that they don't not put much attention to it , even if they do it's not in the point of inefficient allocation or market effects .the last question answer state that people doesn't think about the externality cost of using any public good or common pool resource.

The current picture is that the people of Bangladesh are still not very much concern with the relationship of property rights or market efficiency system.

Analysis of the current situation

Inefficient allocation of resources causes market failure. Like most countries Bangladesh also have some broad economic, social, and environmental goals defined. But if the resources are not allocated in an efficient manner than that creates an obstacle in the way.

The survey shows that most of the general people are unaware of the importance of the relationship of proper property rights and market efficiency. Private property rights give legal rights over the use of certain resources that has direct relation with environment.

The current situation shows that the major factors of production are being affected by the practice of imperfect property rights. It has given agents the power over the market so the free-market concept is not fulfilled. When such control is there no market can meet the optimal level. And the natural force is hampered.

In Bangladesh, we can see that the practice of proper property rights is not given the accurate level of importance. For that general people are not aware with the greater good of neither the practice of property rights nor the costs of imperfect property rights. The economy is been affected by this unawareness.

The proper use of property rights is not only directly related with the market efficiency but also the economic growth as well. The inappropriate use of our natural resource for example the deforestation possibility of the sunder ban forest in now in an alarming point. Where the last natural disaster affected us so badly that the specialists claimed that the loss of the forest will take at least fifty years to recover and therefore we should cut as much less as we can. But that is not happing the present time. If the private property rights were been more efficient than maybe we could hope for a better result.

The general people are not concern with the day-to-day use of resources, and the result of that.

This situation has been stopping out markets to work more efficiently, and the economic growth is there for not a high rate. The proverb level is less than before but if these rights were practice more efficiently than the growth would have been more. in the current situation the prices to necessary goods such as rice,vegetables,spices or even oil,octen,petrol has risen so much that it has our population has become weaker in terms of fulfilling their basic needs.

Conclusion

The practice of imperfect property rights is not only related to the market system. As the market failure includes environmental problems, such as pollution or overexploitation of natural gas; property rights is also related with such other factors. When a well define property right is exchanged so is the facilities of efficiency in the market. So, to prevent that practice of a well define property right is need.

But this will not be achieved unless the concept is clear among not only the specializes fields but also in the general level as they are the daily user of such rights and all the resources.

- The government policy should be practice.ould be practice. Since a government policy can affect the management of natural resources as well as the protection of the environment. • There is a need of some sort of strategic policy to bring the expected level of economic growth. • Large scale policies should therefore be used cautiously because all three types of macro-economic policies; fiscal, monetary and trade could have impacts on natural resource conservation and the environment.
- There as common indications that covenant fiscal policy instruments can be directly applied to enhance the rate of the conservation and the minimization of environmental effects.nce the natural resource management and environmental conservation.
- We can use some strategic policy to achieve the expected level of economic growth.
- The use of macro-economic policies should be carefully handles as all three forms-fiscal, monetary and trade policy can influence the natural resource conservation and environment.
- Fiscal policy can be directly used to improve conservation and reduce environmental impacts. Like the farmers may cut on the use of agro chemicals if these are taxed.the villages may be motivated to plant trees more or,water can be provided to the full incremental cost to discourage wastage

Directions for future research:

The market failure situation is not only caused by the practice imperfect property right, more over that is one of the many reasons, but a major part will be sort out if the concept of property rights specially the private property rights is more discussed. The relation between inefficient practice of private property rights and the use of environmental inputs in primary production should be more cleared. More focused research could be done.

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